

MECHANISM OF DRY FRICTION.

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Annotation.

Mechanics is the oldest physical science that deals with both stationary and moving bodies under the influence of forces. The branch of mechanics that deals with bodies at rest is called statics, while the branch that deals with bodies in motion is called dynamics.

Keywords.

fluid kinematics, fluid mechanics, hydraulics, fluid dynamics, hydrodynamics.

Usual Assumption till now:

Forces of action and reaction between contacting surfaces act normal to the surface.

→ valid for interaction between smooth surfaces

→ in many cases ability of contacting surfaces to support tangential forces

is very important (Ex: Figure above)

Frictional Forces

Tangential forces generated between contacting surfaces.

- occur in the interaction between all real surfaces
- always act in a direction opposite to the direction of motion

Frictional forces are Not Desired in some cases:

• Bearings, power screws, gears, flow of fluids in pipes, propulsion of aircraft and missiles through the atmosphere, etc.

• Friction often results in a loss of energy, which is dissipated in the form of heat

• Friction causes Wear

Frictional forces are Desired in some cases:

- Brakes, clutches, belt drives, wedges
- walking depends on friction between the shoe and the ground

Ideal Machine/Process: Friction small enough to be neglected Real Machine/Process: Friction must be taken into account.

Dry Friction (Coulomb Friction) occurs between unlubricated surfaces of two solids.

Effects of dry friction acting on exterior surfaces of rigid bodies.

Fluid Friction occurs when adjacent layers in a fluid (liquid or gas) move at a different velocities. Fluid friction also depends on viscosity of the fluid.

→ Fluid Mechanics

Internal Friction occurs in all solid materials subjected to cyclic loading, especially in those materials, which have low limits of elasticity .

→ Material Science

Mechanism of Dry Friction.

- Block of weight W placed on horizontal surface. Forces acting on block are its weight and reaction of surface N .

- Small horizontal force P applied to block. For block to remain stationary, in

equilibrium, a horizontal component F of the surface reaction is required. F is a *Static-Friction force*.

- As P increases, static-friction force F increases as well until it reaches a maximum value F_m .

$$F_m = m_s N$$

- Further increase in P causes the block to begin to move as F drops to a smaller *Kinetic-Friction force* F_k .

$$F_k = m_k N$$

μ_s is the Coefficient of Static Friction

μ_k is the Coefficient of Kinetic Friction

Table 8.1. Approximate Values of Coefficient of Static Friction for Dry Surfaces

Metal on metal	0.15–0.60
Metal on wood	0.20–0.60
Metal on stone	0.30–0.70
Metal on leather	0.30–0.60
Wood on wood	0.25–0.50
Wood on leather	0.25–0.50
Stone on stone	0.40–0.70
Earth on earth	0.20–1.00
Rubber on concrete	0.60–0.90

- Maximum static-friction force:

$$F_m = m_s N$$

- Kinetic-friction force:

$$F_k = m_k N$$

$$m_k @ 0.75m_s$$

Maximum static-friction force and kinetic-friction force are:

- proportional to normal force
- dependent on type and condition of contact surfaces
- independent of contact area

A friction coefficient reflects roughness, which is a geometric property of surfaces

When the surfaces are in relative motion, the contacts are more nearly along the tops of the humps, and the t-components of the R 's are smaller than when the surfaces are at rest relative to one another

→ Force necessary to maintain motion is generally less than that required to start the block when the surface irregularities are more nearly in mesh

→ $F_m > F_k$

Four situations can occur when a rigid body is in contact with a horizontal surface:

- No friction, ($P_x = 0$)

- No motion, ($P_x < F_m$)

- Motion impending, ($P_x = F_m$)

- Motion, ($P_x > F_m$)

Equations of Equilibrium Valid

Equations of Equilibrium Valid

Equations of Equilibrium Valid

Equations of Equilibrium Valid

Sometimes convenient to replace normal force N & friction force F by their resultant R :

- No friction - No motion - Motion impending - Motion

$$\tan \phi_s = \frac{F_m}{N} = \frac{\mu_s N}{N}$$

$$\tan \phi_k = \frac{F_k}{N} = \frac{\mu_k N}{N}$$

$$\tan \phi_s = \mu_s$$

$$\tan \phi_k = \mu_k$$

Friction Angles

f_s = angle of static friction, f_k = angle of kinetic friction

Consider block of weight W resting on board with variable inclination angle θ .

- No friction
- No motion
- Motion impending
- Motion

Angle of Repose =
Angle of Static Friction

The reaction R is not vertical anymore, and the forces acting on the block are unbalanced

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